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科学知识图谱指南系列

图 1 免费获取科学计量与知识图谱资料合集

Loet Leydesdorff (Ph.D. Sociology, M.A. Philosophy, and M.Sc. Biochemistry) is Professor at the Amsterdam School of Communications Research (ASCoR) of the University of Amsterdam. He is Visiting Professor of the Institute of Scientific and Technical Information of China (ISTIC) in Beijing and Honorary Fellow of the Science and Technology Policy Research Unit (SPRU) of the University of Sussex. He has published extensively in systems theory, social network analysis, scientometrics, and the sociology of innovation (see for a list of publications at <http://www.leydesdorff.net/list.htm>). With Henry Etzkowitz, he initiated a series of workshops, conferences, and special issues about the Triple Helix of University-Industry-Government Relations. He received the Derek de Solla Price Award for Scientometrics and Informetrics in 2003 and held “The City of Lausanne” Honor Chair at the School of Economics, Université de Lausanne, in 2005. Since 2014, the Web of Science lists him as a highly-cited author at <https://clarivate.com/hcr/>

Source: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-7835-3098>

▪ data Collection

The screenshot displays the Web of Science search interface. At the top right, there are navigation links: Tools, Searches and alerts, Search History, and Marked List. Below this is a header bar with a dropdown menu for 'Select a database' set to 'Web of Science Core Collection' and a button for 'Learn about alerting enhancements!'. The main search area has four tabs: Basic Search (selected), Author Search^{BETA}, Cited Reference Search, and Advanced Search. The search criteria are entered in two rows: the first row contains 'E-2903-2010' and 'Author Identifiers'; the second row contains 'Or', 'Example: oil spill* mediterranean', and 'Topic'. A 'Search' button and 'Search tips' link are to the right. Below the search area, there are options for '+ Add row' and 'Reset'. The 'Timespan' section shows a dropdown for 'All years (1900 - 2020)'. The 'More settings' section includes 'Web of Science Core Collection: Citation Indexes' with checkboxes for 'Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED) --1900-present' and 'Social Science Citation Index (SSCI) --1900-present', both checked. There is also an 'Auto-suggest publication names' dropdown set to 'On'.

Fig. 1 Data collection

Search Tools Searches and alerts Search History Marked List

Results: 338
(from Web of Science Core Collection)

You searched for: AUTHOR IDENTIFIERS: (E-2903-2010)
Timespan: All years. Indexes: SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI.
...Less
[Create an alert](#)

Refine Results

Search within results for...

Filter results by:

- Highly Cited in Field (6)
- Open Access (79)

[Refine](#)

Publication Years

Sort by: **Date** Times Cited Usage Count Relevance More

1 of 34

Select Page [Export...](#) [Add to Marked List](#)

1. **Synergy in the knowledge base of US innovation systems at national, state, and regional levels: The contributions of high-tech manufacturing and knowledge-intensive services**
By: Leydesdorff, Loet; Wagner, Caroline S.; Porto-Gomez, Igone; et al.
JOURNAL OF THE ASSOCIATION FOR INFORMATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY Volume: 70 Issue: 10 Pages: 1108-1123 Published: OCT 2019
[Findit NCKU](#) [Free Full Text from Publisher](#) [View Abstract](#) Times Cited: 1
(from Web of Science Core Collection) [Usage Count](#)

2. **Can topic models be used in research evaluations? Reproducibility, validity, and reliability when compared with semantic maps**
By: Hecking, Tobias; Leydesdorff, Loet
RESEARCH EVALUATION Volume: 28 Issue: 3 Pages: 263-272 Published: JUL 2019
[Findit NCKU](#) [Full Text from Publisher](#) [View Abstract](#) Times Cited: 0
(from Web of Science Core Collection) [Usage Count](#)

3. **The integrated impact indicator revisited(I3*): a non-parametric alternative to the journal impact factor**
By: Leydesdorff, Loet; Bornmann, Lutz; Adams, Jonathan
SCIENTOMETRICS Volume: 119 Issue: 3 Pages: 1669-1694 Published: JUN 2019
[Findit NCKU](#) [Free Full Text from Publisher](#) [View Abstract](#) Times Cited: 0
(from Web of Science Core Collection) [Usage Count](#)

4. **Does the public discuss other topics on climate change than researchers? A comparison of explorative** Times Cited: 1

[Analyze Results](#)
[Create Citation Report](#)

Fig. 2 Results of the data

Table 1 Main Information about the collection (6 Highly Cited in Field, 79 Open Access)

Description	Results
Documents	338
Sources (Journals, Books, etc.)	64
Keywords Plus (ID)	412
Author's Keywords (DE)	493
Period	1980 - 2019
Average citations per documents	41.21
Authors	178
Author Appearances	737
Authors of single-authored documents	3
Authors of multi-authored documents	175
Single-authored documents	94
Documents per Author	1.9
Authors per Document	0.527
Co-Authors per Documents	2.18
Collaboration Index	0.717
Document types	
ARTICLE	279
ARTICLE; PROCEEDINGS PAPER	5
BOOK REVIEW	6
CORRECTION	1
EDITORIAL MATERIAL	17
LETTER	23
MEETING ABSTRACT	1
NEWS ITEM	1
NOTE	2
REVIEW	3

■ Annual trends

Fig. 3 Publications trend of Loet Leydesdorff

Fig. 4 Citations trend of Loet Leydesdorff

Table 2 Publication and citation trends of Loet Leydesdorff

#	Year	Recs	Percent	TLCS	TGCS	#	Year	Recs	Percent	TLCS	TGCS
1	1980	1	0.3	0	0	20	2001	4	1.2	6	30
2	1981	1	0.3	1	3	21	2002	5	1.5	24	74
3	1982	1	0.3	2	2	22	2003	7	2.1	31	236
4	1984	1	0.3	2	2	23	2004	3	0.9	31	184
5	1986	1	0.3	37	64	24	2005	12	3.6	77	838
6	1987	5	1.5	19	109	25	2006	12	3.6	153	1111
7	1988	1	0.3	0	0	26	2007	13	3.8	45	520
8	1989	5	1.5	66	219	27	2008	13	3.8	98	713
9	1990	4	1.2	44	103	28	2009	19	5.6	168	1147
10	1991	4	1.2	43	80	29	2010	19	5.6	167	1141
11	1992	5	1.5	26	39	30	2011	22	6.5	179	955
12	1993	3	0.9	33	95	31	2012	18	5.3	108	782
13	1994	7	2.1	50	139	32	2013	26	7.7	75	681
14	1995	2	0.6	8	10	33	2014	24	7.1	73	520
15	1996	4	1.2	9	105	34	2015	21	6.2	27	391
16	1997	5	1.5	43	151	35	2016	18	5.3	43	228
17	1998	4	1.2	18	367	36	2017	17	5	15	110
18	1999	2	0.6	11	31	37	2018	11	3.3	4	44
19	2000	7	2.1	78	2690	38	2019	11	3.3	3	16

- **Journals**
- **Citing Journals**

Fig. 5 Journals bibliographic coupling analysis (Nodes size was appropriate with number of publications, and the color is shown the average publication year of the journal)

Note: journal of the American society for information science (JASIST), journal of informetrics (JOI), scientometrics (SCI) and jasss-the journal of artificial societies and social simulation (JASSS).

Table 3 Citing journals of Loet Leydesdorff

Journals	Documents	Citations	Avg. pub. Year	Avg. citations
SCI	87	2416	2005.94	27.77
JASIST	85	3872	2010.78	45.55
JOI	41	1451	2013.49	35.39
RESEARCH POLICY	15	4195	2002.00	279.67
PROFESIONAL DE LA INFORMACION	8	94	2013.50	11.75
SOCIAL SCIENCE INFORMATION SUR LES SCIENCES SOCIALES	8	78	2002.38	9.75
SYSTEMS RESEARCH AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCE	6	79	2005.00	13.17
TECHNOLOGICAL FORECASTING AND SOCIAL CHANGE	6	144	2012.17	24.00
PLOS ONE	5	109	2014.40	21.80
RESEARCH EVALUATION	4	64	2013.50	16.00
SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY & HUMAN VALUES	4	79	1990.25	19.75
TECHNOLOGY ANALYSIS & STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT	4	78	2008.00	19.50
JOURNAL OF DOCUMENTATION	3	78	2002.67	26.00
KYBERNETES	3	15	2008.67	5.00
MINERVA	3	241	2007.67	80.33
CURRENT SCIENCE	2	20	2000.50	10.00
EMBO REPORTS	2	40	2014.50	20.00
ENTROPY	2	35	2009.00	17.50
JASSS	2	7	2003.00	3.50
JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND EVOLUTIONARY SYSTEMS	2	20	1994.00	10.00
PUBLIC UNDERSTANDING OF SCIENCE	2	83	2007.50	41.50
RECHERCHE	2	3	1987.00	1.50
SCIENCE AND PUBLIC POLICY	2	9	2014.00	4.50
SOCIAL STUDIES OF SCIENCE	2	40	2002.00	20.00

Fig. 6 Location of citing journals on the global journals map

Fig. 7 Journals categories of the publications

Note: The Stirling-Rao diversity (over the full matrix) is 0.560; "True diversity" (Zhang et al., 2016) is 2.271.

2008 The Regents of the University of California and SciTech Strategies. Map updated by SciTech Strategies, OST, and CNS in 2011.

Legend

Circle area: Fractional record count
 Unclassified = 5
 Minimum = 1
 Maximum = 114
 Color: Discipline
 See end of PDF for color legend.

CNS (cns.lu.edu)

Fig. 10 Location of cited journals of on the global journals map (Rao-Stirling diversity is: 0.1538)

Table 4 High cited sources the citing papers

Journals	Links	Total link strength	Citations
SCIENTOMETRICS	82	41720	1622
JASIST	82	40219	1498
RES POLICY	82	20168	733
J INFORMETR	80	17109	535
SCIENCE	82	6934	211
SOC NETWORKS	81	3972	163
NATURE	82	4155	142
SOC STUD SCI	82	3994	141
SCI PUBL POLICY	82	3569	112
SOC SCI INFORM	82	3436	110
RES EVALUAT	77	3058	83
PLOS ONE	67	2882	76
P NATL ACAD SCI USA	73	2664	73
TECHNICAL CHANGE EC	76	1747	67
BELL SYST TECH J	79	1545	65
INFORM PROCESS LETT	79	2051	61
ANNU REV INFORM SCI	79	2655	58
INFORM PROCESS MANAG	73	2340	58
EVOLUTIONARY EC CHAO	73	1515	57
AM ECON REV	79	1888	55
INT J GEN SYST	72	1488	54
CHALLENGE SCIENTOMET	78	1340	53
PSYCHOMETRIKA	79	1627	53
INTELLECTUAL SOCIAL	82	1660	51

- Journals dual-overlay

Fig. 11 Journals dual overlay map of Loet Leydesdorff

- Collaboration Analysis
- Authors collaboration

Fig. 12 Authors collaboration network of Loet Leydesdorff

Table 5 Co-authors of Loet Leydesdorff

Authors	Links	Documents	Avg. pub. year	Avg. citations
Bornmann, Lutz	28	58	2014.74	23.40
Wagner, Caroline S.	16	23	2013.26	45.17
Zhou, Ping	4	13	2009.92	47.31
Park, Han Woo	8	12	2012.17	41.33
Rafols, Ismael	10	12	2011.92	108.25
Opthof, Tobias	3	10	2011.80	47.30
Ivanova, Inga A.	5	9	2015.56	11.56
Hellsten, Iina	8	7	2011.14	27.14
Comins, Jordan A.	8	6	2017.17	3.17
De Nooy, Wouter	8	6	2013.67	10.50
Marx, Werner	7	6	2014.33	22.17
Rotolo, Daniele	6	6	2014.83	16.67
Van Den Besselaar, Peter	2	6	2006.67	33.50
Wouters, Paul	3	6	2001.00	17.50
De Moya-anegon, Felix	4	5	2012.60	43.80
Dolfsma, Wilfred	2	5	2008.80	32.40
Heimeriks, Gaston	5	5	2012.40	12.00
Lucio-arias, Diana	2	5	2009.80	31.60
Meyer, Martin	1	5	2007.80	69.00

▪ **Institutions collaboration**

Fig. 13 Institutions collaboration network of Loet Leydesdorff

▪ **Countries/Regions collaboration**

Fig. 14 Countries collaboration network of Loet Leydesdorff

Table 6 Countries/regions have collaborated with Loet Leydesdorff (Documents>1)

Countries/Regions	Links	Documents	Avg. pub. Year	Avg. citations
NETHERLANDS	28	289	2010.50	44.83
GERMANY	12	63	2014.25	24.19
USA	15	52	2011.88	88.35
ENGLAND	9	31	2012.87	61.29
PEOPLES R CHINA	4	20	2010.95	33.95
BELGIUM	12	14	2010.86	26.29
SOUTH KOREA	4	14	2012.21	38.71
SPAIN	8	13	2013.77	31.54
RUSSIA	5	10	2015.50	12.10
SWITZERLAND	3	9	2008.22	69.78
AUSTRALIA	9	4	2008.00	42.75
HUNGARY	2	4	2011.25	21.25
ITALY	4	4	2015.25	11.00
NORWAY	3	4	2015.00	16.75
SWEDEN	5	4	2013.00	44.50
FINLAND	8	3	2008.00	36.00
IRELAND	2	2	2017.50	6.00
MEXICO	4	2	2006.00	13.00
SCOTLAND	1	2	2010.50	79.00

ID	Agglomeration	Country	Publications ▼
AD8361	AMSTERDAM	NETHERLANDS	324
AD4662	MUNICH	GERMANY	55
AAPOLY23731	BRIGHTON	UNITED-KINGDOM	21
AD13304	COLUMBUS	UNITED-STATES	15
AD16876	WASHINGTON-BETHESDA	UNITED-STATES	13
AD2074	BEIJING	CHINA	13
AD1081	LEUVEN	BELGIUM	11
AD9995	TAEGU	SOUTH-KOREA	11
AD8563	UTRECHT	NETHERLANDS	9
AD4957	STUTTGART	GERMANY	7
AAPOINT20175	VLADIVOSTOK	RUSSIA	6
AD12830	BLOOMINGTON	UNITED-STATES	6
AD8483	ROTTERDAM-LEIDEN-DELFT-DEN HAAG	NETHERLANDS	6
AD10167	MADRID	SPAIN	5
AD15709	PHILADELPHIA	UNITED-STATES	5
AD2144	HANGZHOU	CHINA	5
AD4490	KARLSRUHE	GERMANY	5

Fig. 15 Countries/regions collaboration network on the world map

Note: Visualized by <http://37.187.79.5/netscitypg/index.php>

Fig. 16 Cities collaboration network on the world map

Fig. 19 Keywords average publications year of Loet Leydesdorff

Fig. 20 Keywords average citations of Loet Leydesdorff

- Terms analysis

Fig. 21 Terms analysis of the publications (terms were from titles and abstracts of the publications)

Fig. 22 Terms density analysis of the publications (terms were from titles and abstracts of the publications)

- Citation analysis
- Citing articles analysis

Documents bibliographic coupling

Fig. 23 Bibliographic coupling network of 329 papers of Loet Leydesdorff

Table 7 High cited papers in each cluster

Documents	Cluster	Citations	Documents	Cluster	Citations	Documents	Cluster	Citations	Documents	Cluster	Citations
Rafols (2010)	1	207	Etzkowitz (2000)	2	2380	Wagner (2005)	3	436	Leydesdorff (1998)	4	177
Rafols (2012)	1	204	Etzkowitz (1998)	2	181	Zhou (2006)	3	311	Leydesdorff (1989)	4	107
Mingers (2015)	1	121	Leydesdorff (2000a)	2	171	Leydesdorff (2009e)	3	303	Leydesdorff (2006e)	4	103
Leydesdorff (2011e)	1	119	Leydesdorff (2006)	2	145	Leydesdorff (2007c)	3	222	Leydesdorff (1997a)	4	103
Opthof (2010)	1	117	Leydesdorff (2011n)	2	107	Leydesdorff (2006b)	3	201	Leydesdorff (1987b)	4	84
Leydesdorff (2009b)	1	109	Leydesdorff (2003a)	2	100	Leydesdorff (2008b)	3	157	Lucio-Arias (2008)	4	79
Leydesdorff (2011l)	1	105	Leydesdorff (2003)	2	99	Leydesdorff (2008g)	3	150	Park (2005)	4	77
Leydesdorff (2013h)	1	103	Park (2010)	2	97	Abbasi (2012)	3	140	Leydesdorff (1990b)	4	71
Bornmann (2012)	1	95	Leydesdorff (2006a)	2	95	Rafols (2009)	3	110	Van Den Besselaar (1996)	4	64
Leydesdorff (2011a)	1	91	Leydesdorff (2006f)	2	92	Leydesdorff (2009g)	3	98	Leydesdorff (1986)	4	64
Leydesdorff (2010)	1	91	Leydesdorff (2009c)	2	80	Leydesdorff (2005d)	3	98	Leydesdorff (2006d)	4	63
Bornmann (2013b)	1	81	Kwon (2012)	2	64	Leydesdorff (2008h)	3	90	Leydesdorff (1994c)	4	62
Leydesdorff (2011j)	1	80	Leydesdorff (2010d)	2	64	Egghe (2009)	3	76	Leydesdorff (2004a)	4	59
Leydesdorff (2010a)	1	67	Lengyel (2011)	2	56	Leydesdorff (2008c)	3	71	Leydesdorff (2005c)	4	57
Leydesdorff (2010f)	1	66	Leydesdorff (2010i)	2	51	Leydesdorff (2010c)	3	65	Leydesdorff (2005e)	4	57
Leydesdorff (2014f)	1	62	Leydesdorff (2011i)	2	49	Leydesdorff (2009)	3	65	Amsterdamska (1989)	4	56
Leydesdorff (2012g)	1	53	Leydesdorff (2010g)	2	49	Leydesdorff (2004)	3	65	Leydesdorff (1993b)	4	55
Halffman (2010)	1	53	Dolfsma (2009)	2	46	Leydesdorff (2007e)	3	64	Leydesdorff (1991)	4	44
Van Den Besselaar (2009)	1	53	Frenken (2000)	2	45	Leydesdorff (2004b)	3	60	Leydesdorff (1989b)	4	33
Leydesdorff (2013a)	1	52	Leydesdorff (2005b)	2	41	Leydesdorff (2008d)	3	53	Wouters (1994)	4	32
Leydesdorff (2012e)	1	49	Leydesdorff (2000)	2	41	Leydesdorff (2007d)	3	49	Leydesdorff (2000b)	4	27
Marx (2014)	1	48	Ivanova (2014)	2	37	Leydesdorff (2011f)	3	46	Leydesdorff (2002c)	4	26
Chen (2014)	1	48	Leydesdorff (1997c)	2	35	Wagner (2015a)	3	44	Leydesdorff (1996a)	4	24
Bornmann (2013c)	1	48	Leydesdorff (2007f)	2	33	Park (2013)	3	44	Leydesdorff (2002a)	4	23
Leydesdorff (2011)	1	47	Lucio-Arias (2009a)	2	31	Leydesdorff (2007g)	3	44	Leydesdorff (1994)	4	21
Bornmann (2011a)	1	47	Strand (2013)	2	30	Hellsten (2010)	3	42	Park (2016)	4	20
Bornmann (2010a)	1	47	Leydesdorff (2010b)	2	30	Leydesdorff (2013k)	3	41	Lucio-Arias (2009)	4	19
Bornmann (2011)	1	45	Leydesdorff (2013e)	2	28	Leydesdorff (2009a)	3	40	Lucio-Arias (2007)	4	19
Leydesdorff (2011g)	1	43	Leydesdorff (1993)	2	26	Leydesdorff (2008f)	3	38	Leydesdorff (2003e)	4	19
Bornmann (2014)	1	40	Leydesdorff (2014g)	2	25	Park (2009)	3	37	Leydesdorff (1987a)	4	19

Direct citation network (CitNetExplorer)

Fig. 24 Direct citation network of TOP 100 high cited publications of Loet Leydesdorff

Fig. 25 Direct citation network of TOP 100 high cited publications from blue cluster

Fig. 26 Direct citation network of TOP 100 high cited publications from green cluster

Fig. 27 Direct citation network of 86 publications from purple cluster

Fig. 28 Direct citation network of 13 publications from orange cluster

Table 8 Papers from the orange cluster

Authors	Title	Year
Wagner, Cs; Leydesdorff, L	seismology as a dynamic, distributed area of scientific research	2003
Wagner, Cs; Leydesdorff, L	network structure, self-organization, and the growth of international collaboration in science	2005
Leydesdorff, L; Wagner, Cs	international collaboration in science and the formation of a core group	2008
Abbasi, A; Hossain, L; Leydesdorff, L	betweenness centrality as a driver of preferential attachment in the evolution of research collaboration networks	2012
Leydesdorff, L; Wagner, Cs; Park, Hw; Adams, J	international collaboration in science: the global map and the network	2013
Park, Hw; Leydesdorff, L	decomposing social and semantic networks in emerging "big data" research	2013
Leydesdorff, L; Park, Hw; Wagner, C	international coauthorship relations in the social sciences citation index: is internationalization leading the network?	2014
Adams, J; Gurney, K; Hook, D; Leydesdorff, L	international collaboration clusters in africa	2014
Wagner, Cs; Park, Hw; Leydesdorff, L	the continuing growth of global cooperation networks in research: a conundrum for national governments	2015
Park, Hw; Yoon, J; Leydesdorff, L	the normalization of co-authorship networks in the bibliometric evaluation: the government stimulation programs of china and korea	2016
Velez-Cuartas, G; Lucio-Arias, D; Leydesdorff, L	regional and global science: publications from latin america and the caribbean in the scielo citation index and the web of science	2016
Wagner, Cs; Whetsell, Ta; Leydesdorff, L	growth of international collaboration in science: revisiting six specialties	2017
Leydesdorff, L; Bornmann, L; Wagner, Cs	the relative influences of government funding and international collaboration on citation impact	2019

Direct citation network (HistCite)

Fig. 29 Direct citation network of Top 50 high cited papers

Nodes: 50, Links: 192; LCS, top 50; Min: 12, Max: 45 (LCS scaled)

Table 9 Detailed information of publications in the direct citation network

No.	Nodes number	Publications	LCS	GCS
1.	5	LEYDESDORFF L, 1986, SCIENTOMETRICS, V9, P103	37	64
2.	7	LEYDESDORFF L, 1987, SCIENTOMETRICS, V11, P295	16	84
3.	13	AMSTERDAMSKA O, 1989, SCIENTOMETRICS, V15, P449	13	56
4.	16	LEYDESDORFF L, 1989, RES POLICY, V18, P209	35	107
5.	18	LEYDESDORFF L, 1990, SCI TECHNOL HUM VAL, V15, P305	19	71
6.	24	LEYDESDORFF L, 1991, SOC NETWORKS, V13, P301	28	44
7.	31	LEYDESDORFF L, 1993, SCIENTOMETRICS, V26, P135	14	55
8.	32	LEYDESDORFF L, 1993, J THEOR SOC BEHAV, V23, P47	17	26
9.	35	LEYDESDORFF L, 1994, RES POLICY, V23, P217	26	62
10.	47	Leydesdorff L, 1997, SCIENTOMETRICS, V38, P155	19	35
11.	49	Leydesdorff L, 1997, J AM SOC INFORM SCI, V48, P418	17	103
12.	53	Leydesdorff L, 1998, SCIENTOMETRICS, V43, P5	13	177
13.	57	Etzkowitz H, 2000, RES POLICY, V29, P109	37	2380
14.	59	Leydesdorff L, 2000, SCIENTOMETRICS, V47, P265	12	27
15.	60	Frenken K, 2000, RES POLICY, V29, P331	13	45
16.	71	Leydesdorff L, 2002, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V53, P987	12	23
17.	79	Leydesdorff L, 2003, SCIENTOMETRICS, V58, P445	18	100
18.	82	Leydesdorff L, 2004, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V55, P991	13	65
19.	88	Leydesdorff L, 2005, SCI COMMUN, V27, P64	12	57
20.	91	Park HW, 2005, SCIENTOMETRICS, V65, P3	15	77
21.	93	Leydesdorff L, 2005, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V56, P1469	13	24
22.	94	Wagner CS, 2005, RES POLICY, V34, P1608	18	436
23.	97	Zhou P, 2006, RES POLICY, V35, P83	19	311
24.	98	Leydesdorff L, 2006, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V57, P601	37	103
25.	99	Leydesdorff L, 2006, RES POLICY, V35, P181	21	92
26.	101	Leydesdorff L, 2006, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V57, P1470	14	36
27.	102	Leydesdorff L, 2006, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V57, P1616	15	201
28.	106	Leydesdorff L, 2006, RES POLICY, V35, P1538	23	95
29.	115	Leydesdorff L, 2007, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V58, P1303	14	222
30.	122	Leydesdorff L, 2008, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V59, P278	34	150
31.	127	Leydesdorff L, 2008, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V59, P1810	21	71
32.	136	Leydesdorff L, 2009, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V60, P348	19	303
33.	138	Leydesdorff L, 2009, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V60, P778	20	80
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35.	144	Rafols I, 2009, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V60, P1823	45	110
36.	161	Ophhof T, 2010, J INFORMETR, V4, P423	24	117
37.	163	Leydesdorff L, 2010, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V61, P1622	15	65
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39.	168	Leydesdorff L, 2010, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V61, P2138	15	30
40.	172	Lengyel B, 2011, REG STUD, V45, P677	16	56
41.	174	Leydesdorff L, 2011, J INFORMETR, V5, P87	13	105
42.	177	Leydesdorff L, 2011, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V62, P217	13	80
43.	179	Leydesdorff L, 2011, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V62, P846	20	49
44.	183	Leydesdorff L, 2011, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V62, P1370	30	119
45.	189	Bornmann L, 2011, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V62, P1954	15	47
46.	190	Leydesdorff L, 2011, J AM SOC INF SCI TEC, V62, P2133	18	91
47.	198	Leydesdorff L, 2012, J INFORMETR, V6, P318	13	53
48.	199	Bornmann L, 2012, J INFORMETR, V6, P333	13	95
49.	206	Rafols I, 2012, RES POLICY, V41, P1262	19	204
50.	217	Bornmann L, 2013, J INFORMETR, V7, P158	13	81

▪ **Cited articles analysis**

RPYS analysis

Fig. 30 Reference Publication Year Spectroscopy (RPYS) analysis of the cited references

Authors co-citation analysis

Fig. 31 Authors co-citation analysis of Loet Leydesdorff

References co-citation analysis (VOSviewer)

Fig. 32 Reference co-citation analysis of Loet Leydesdorff

References co-citation analysis (CiteSpace)

Fig. 33 Reference co-citation clusters of Loet Leydesdorff

Fig. 34 Reference co-citation clusters of Loet Leydesdorff

Fig. 35 Top 5 high cited references in each cluster

Fig. 36 Timeline Visualization of the reference's co-citation analysis

Top 25 References with the Strongest Citation Bursts

Fig. 37 Top 25 References with the strongest citation bursts

▪ **Scientometric mapping tools**

▪ **CiteSpace**

<https://sourceforge.net/projects/citespace/files/latest/download>

▪ **VOSviewer**

<https://www.vosviewer.com/>

▪ **CitNetExplorer**

<https://www.citnetexplorer.nl/>

▪ **NetsCity**

http://37.187.79.5/netscitypg/importer_fichier_1_choice.php?lang=en

▪ **leydesdorff.net**

<https://www.leydesdorff.net/overlaytoolkit/index.htm>

▪ **HistCite**

▪ Appendix

First Author papers of Loet Leydesdorff [1-201], other papers [202-338].

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